

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Carbohydrazide by Chloramine-T and Bromamine-T in Acid and Buffered Aqueous Media

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Kinetics of oxidation of carbohydrazide (CH) by chloramine-T (CAT) and bromamine-T (BAT) have been investigated in aqueous medium under varying conditions. The kinetics of reactions in aqueous perchloric acid show first order in [oxidant] and fractional order in [CH]. But the rate dependences in $[H^+]$ are concentration dependent. At low $[HClO_4]$, oxidation by both CAT and BAT shows inverse fractional order in $[H^+]$, and at $[HClO_4] > 0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the rate shows zero to fractional order. In buffered media, the reactions are first order in [oxidant] and fractional to first order in [CH], but are independent of pH. Mechanisms consistent with the observed results have been considered and the related rate laws deduced. Coefficients of the rate-limiting steps and the corresponding activation parameters are also calculated.

THE chemistry of hydrazine and its derivatives is of interest due to their wide applications and biological activities¹⁻⁴. The chemical research with these potential reagents has been mostly focussed on structural aspects of their metal complexes in the solid state. The mechanistic aspects of their reactions in solution are not well-established. Recently some work has been initiated in our laboratories based on the latter aspects⁵⁻¹². As a part of these efforts, we report herein the kinetics of oxidation of carbohydrazide by *N*-chloro- and *N*-bromotoluene-*p*-sulphonamides in aqueous medium under varying conditions.

Experimental

Analytical grade chloramine-T (Fluka, AG) was used. Bromamine-T was prepared by the partial debromination of dibromamine-T¹³, the latter being obtained by the bromination of chloramine-T¹⁴. Stock solutions of the oxidants (0.10 mol dm^{-3}) were prepared in double-distilled water and standardised by the iodometric method. Carbohydrazide³ was prepared by the literature method and its aqueous stock solution (0.50 mol dm^{-3}) was employed. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Preliminary studies of the reactions showed that the ionic strength of the medium had no significant effect on the rates of reactions.

Kinetic measurement: Kinetic studies were made in glass-stoppered pyrex tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with $[\text{substrate}] \gg [\text{oxidant}]$ (5–100 fold excess). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution (5×10^{-4} – $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to solutions

containing known amounts of carbohydrazide (0.01 – 0.20 mol dm^{-3}), perchloric acid (0.0005 – 0.10 mol dm^{-3}) or buffer solution (HCl–KCl or HCl–biphthalate or acetate buffers) and water-thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for at least two half-lives by the iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidants at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods, the values being reproducible within $\pm 4\%$ error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: Stoichiometry of carbohydrazide-oxidant reactions was determined by thermally equilibrating varying ratios of reactants at different $[HClO_4]$ or buffer solutions. Estimation of unreacted oxidant in the reaction mixture showed that one mole of the substrate reacts with four moles of oxidants. The observed stoichiometry is represented by equation (1).

where, $\text{Ar} = p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br .

Nitrogen evolved during the reaction was determined quantitatively using Schiff's nitrometer. A slow and steady current of pure and dry CO_2 was passed through the reaction vessel to sweep off N_2 to the nitrometer filled with 50% KOH, where CO_2 was completely absorbed. The volume of N_2 was noted and compared with the theoretical value. Toluene-*p*-sulphonamide (TSA), the reduced product of the oxidants, was detected by paper chromatography using benzyl alcohol saturated with water as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ether as the spray reagent ($R_f = 0.91$).

TABLE 3—KINETIC DATA AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF CARBOHYDRAZIDE (CH) BY CAT, BAT AND HYPOCHLORITE ION (COMPUTED FROM k_{eff} IN AQUEOUS PERCHLORIC ACID AND FROM k_{obs} IN AQUEOUS BUFFERED MEDIA)

Orders (#) Observed in	In $[\text{HClO}_4]$ ($\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) range						In buffered media in pH range						
	CAT		BAT		HOCI		CAT		BAT		HOCI		
	0.10-0.50	1.0-5.0	0.10-5.0	1.0-5.0	0.10-1.0	1.0-5.0	1.5-2.2 ^a	2.4-3.4 ^b	3.4-5.2 ^c	3.4-5.2 ^c	1.5-2.2 ^a	2.3-3.4 ^b	3.4-5.2 ^c
[Oxidant]	1.0(1.0)	1.0(1.0)	1.0(1.0)	1.0(1.0)	1.0(1.0)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
[CH]	0.33(0.90)	0.94(0.80)	0.31(0.80)	0.77(1.4)	0.70(0.70)	1.0	0.51	0.50	0.31	1.0	0.58	0.54	0
[H ⁺]	-0.67(-0.80)	0.04(0.06)	-0.62(-0.70)	-0.56(-0.70)	-0.10(-0.10)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

	Activation parameters					
	CAT		BAT		HOCI	
	0.10-0.50	1.0-5.0	0.10-0.50	1.0-5.0	0.10-0.50	1.0-5.0
E_a^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	36.2	42.5	42.6	37.9	40.2	44.5
$\log A$	0.37	0.80	6.0	0.14	1.7	4.6
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	31.9	41.7	36.9	36.0	38.0	44.0
ΔS^\ddagger (JK mol ⁻¹)	-252.7	-231.9	-142.9	-248.5	-219.6	-157.7
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	103.4	107.3	82.2	107.6	101.2	90.2

Values in parentheses were computed from k_{obs} . ^aKCl-HCl buffer, ^bBipthalate-HCl buffer, ^cAcetate buffer.

TABLE 5—CALCULATED CONSTANTS OF RATE-LIMITING STEPS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES FOR OXIDATION OF CARBOHYDRAZIDE (CH) BY CAT AND BAT IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM UNDER VARIOUS CONDITIONS

Temp. K	In $[\text{HClO}_4]$ ($\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) range					
	CAT		BAT		HOCI	
	0.10-0.50	1.0-5.0	0.10-0.50	1.0-5.0	0.10-0.50	1.0-5.0
$\times 10^7 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	k_s	k_s	k_s	k_s	k_s	k_s
	4.1	6.3	—	—	—	—
	4.8	9.2	—	—	—	—
	6.4	12.5	—	—	—	—
	9.1	15.9	0.50	16.9	1.2	1.4
	—	—	1.8	22.5	1.5	2.0
	—	—	2.0	29.7	1.9	2.6
	—	—	—	42.5	2.8	—

	Buffered media in the pH range					
	CAT		BAT		HOCI	
	2.4-3.4	3.4-5.2	3.4-5.2	3.4-5.2	3.4-5.2	3.4-5.2
$\times 10^7 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	k_s	k_s	k_s	k_s	k_s	k_s
	—	—	—	—	—	—
	—	—	—	—	—	—
	3.5	4.2	—	—	—	—
	5.1	6.7	6.2	5.3	4.7	3.3
	6.5	8.9	7.2	7.8	6.0	6.5
	—	—	—	11.4	—	—

TABLE 4—VALUES OF k_{obs} FOR OXIDATION OF CARBOHYDRAZIDE (CH) BY CAT (AT 293 K) AND BAT (AT 293 K) IN BUFFERED MEDIA*

pH	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$		[Oxidant] ₀ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	[CH] ₀ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$ at pH			BAT 4.45°
	CAT ^a	BAT ^b			1.80°	3.00 ^d	4.05°	
1.50°	6.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
1.80°	5.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
2.00°	5.8	—	0.50	5.0(2.0)	5.7	8.9	10.0	6.5
2.20°	6.3	—	1.0	5.0(2.0)	5.8	8.8	10.3	6.4
			2.0	5.0(2.0)	5.8	9.1	10.4	6.6
2.40 ^d	10.1	—	4.0	5.0(2.0)	6.0	9.2	11.0	6.7
2.70 ^d	9.4	—	1.0	3.0(1.0)	3.6	7.1	8.5	5.4
3.00 ^d	8.8	—	1.0	5.0(2.0)	5.8	8.8	10.3	6.4
3.40 ^d	8.9	—	1.0	10.0(5.0)	10.4	11.7	14.3	8.4
			1.0	20.0(10.0)	20.9	18.2	21.5	11.6
3.42°	10.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
4.05°	10.3	6.4	—	—	—	—	—	—
4.45°	10.4	6.4	—	—	—	—	—	—
4.99°	11.3	6.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
5.23°	—	7.2	—	—	—	—	—	—

*Values in parenthesis are [CH] for BAT oxidation.

^a $10^3[\text{CAT}]_0=20[\text{CH}]_0=1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. ^b $10^3[\text{BAT}]_0=50[\text{CH}]_0=1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. ^cKCl-HCl buffer. ^dBiphthalate-HCl buffer. ^eAcetate buffer.

The observed results at low $[\text{H}^+]$ can be explained by two-pathway mechanism: steps (i) and (ii), and steps (iii) and (iv) and subsequent fast steps (vii and viii) leading to final products. Based on these steps the combined rate law (2) has been deduced.

$$-\frac{d[\text{oxidant}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{oxidant}][\text{S}]}{[\text{H}^+]} + k_3 [\text{oxidant}] \quad (2)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = K_1 k_2 \frac{[\text{S}]}{[\text{H}^+]} + k_3 = k' \frac{[\text{S}]}{[\text{H}^+]} + k_3 \quad (3)$$

where, $k' = K_1 k_2$. The rate law (3) is consistent with the observed results (Figs. 1 and 2). Constants k' and k_3 were calculated from the plots of k_{eff} vs $[\text{S}]$. Further, k' and k_3 were computed at different temperatures by varying $[\text{substrate}]$ at each temperature and the latter values were employed to compute the activation parameters (Table 3).

As the $[\text{H}^+]$ is increased further, equilibrium of step (i) lies towards left and steps (i) and (ii) get transformed into step (vi). This is evident from the observed almost independence of rate on $[\text{H}^+]$. Hence kinetics in the second acid range can also be accounted by two-pathway mechanism, i.e. by the two competitive steps (iii) and (vi) followed by the fast steps (vii) and (viii) as shown in Scheme 1. The related combined rate law is given by equation (4).

$$-\frac{d[\text{oxidant}]}{dt} = k_3 [\text{oxidant}] + k_4 [\text{oxidant}][\text{S}] \quad (4)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_3 + k_4 [\text{S}] \quad (5)$$

The plot of k_{eff} vs $[\text{S}]$ was linear in conformity with the rate law (5) (Fig. 2). From the slope and intercept of the plot, the k_3 and k_4 were calculated.

Fig. 1. Plots of (i) $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs pH and (ii) k_{obs} vs $1/[\text{H}^+]_{\text{eff}}$; $10^3[\text{CAT}]_0=20[\text{CH}]_0=1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[\text{BAT}]_0=50[\text{CH}]_0=1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; Temp. = 303 K.

Fig. 2. (i) Plots of k_{obs} vs $[CH]_0$: $10^4 [CAT]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^4 [HClO_4] = 0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. (a) 283 K, (b) 303 K; $10^4 [BAT]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^4 [HClO_4] = 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. (c) 288 K. (ii) Plots of k_{obs} vs $[CH]_0$, Temp. = 293 K, $10^4 [CAT]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = (d) 3.00, (e) 4.05; $10^4 [BAT]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = (f) 4.45

The substrate concentrations were varied at different temperatures even under these conditions and k_3 and k_4 were evaluated at each temperature (Table 5). The latter values were employed to compute the activation parameters as described earlier (Table 3).

Buffered media: Oxidation of carbohydrazide by the oxidants in buffered media followed first order kinetics in [oxidant] and fractional to first order in [substrate], but the rate was independent of pH. Kinetics of oxidation in the buffered medium except at low pH were similar to those in the second $[H^+]$ range in the acid medium. The results in the pH range 1.5–2.2 (HCl–KCl buffer) may be explained by step (vi) and other subsequent fast steps shown in Scheme 1; whereas results in other buffered media can be explained by two-pathway mechanism, i.e. through two competitive steps (iii) and (vi) followed by a number of fast steps as shown in Scheme 1. Similar calculations of the coefficients of the rate-limiting steps and the related activation parameters were made even under these conditions (Tables 3 and 5).

Comparison and conclusion: Comparison of the values of k_3 and k_4 (Table 5) reveals that bromamine-T is a better oxidant than chloramine-T, i.e. BAT donates Br^+ species much more readily than CAT does Cl^+ . Similar trends have been observed for oxidation of other substrates by these oxidants and by benzene analogues of them, namely, chloramine-B and bromamine-B^{6,7,9–11}.

Negative ΔS^\ddagger values (Table 3) indicate that the transition states are more ordered than the reactants due to decrease in the number of degrees of freedom. Relatively high positive values for free energy of activation may signal bond-breaking in the formation of transition states.

Kinetics of oxidation of carbohydrazide by hypochlorite ion¹⁰ have also been investigated under identical conditions in both the acid and buffered media. The results (Table 3) are similar to those for chloramine-T oxidations. The latter can also be explained by reaction steps similar to that suggested in Scheme 1 and the related rate laws.

Comparison of kinetic data for the oxidation of carbohydrazide by chloramine-T and bromamine-T with those for the oxidations of thiocarbohydrazide (thio-analogue)⁸ and their lower homologues, semicarbazide and thiosemicarbazide^{6,7}, under similar conditions, reveals that carbohydrazide oxidation follows relatively complicated kinetics while other oxidations show simple and straight forward kinetic behaviour. This may be due to the fact that the carbohydrazide oxidations are sensitive to the changes in $[H^+]$ unlike in other oxidations. Similar trends were observed in the oxidations of these substrates by other halosulphonamides in aqueous medium.

The inverse rate dependence in $[H^+]$ generally observed in the present and earlier investigations indicates that the terminal NH_2 groups are the attacking points in carbohydrazide oxidations^{6,7,10}. It is also evident from the present study that the increase of rate with increase in $[H^+]$ or change in kinetics may be due to change in the form of oxidising species as $[H^+]$ is varied. At low $[H^+]$, the oxidants mostly react in the undissociated $ArSO_2NNaX$ form, whereas at high $[H^+]$, it is likely that they react mostly in the form of $ArSO_2NH_2X^+$, or X^+ species produced in the preequilibrium disproportionating steps.

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